

**OPTIMIZED SURGICAL TACTICS IN PATIENTS WITH
ILEOSTOMY****Botirov Zh.A.****Erkinov Zh.R.****Madazimov M.M.****Andijan State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18478296>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29st January 2026Accepted: 30th January 2026Online: 31th January 2026**KEYWORDS**

The study aims to improve the outcomes of surgical treatment for intestinal diseases by optimizing surgical tactics

ABSTRACT

The formation of an ileostomy is often a necessary and sometimes the only possible method for correcting intestinal pathology. According to summary statistics from several studies, among the conditions leading to ileostomy formation, colon cancer accounts for 43–76%, and benign tumors for 12–27%. Urgent intestinal conditions requiring ileostomy formation comprise 6–21% [3;4;7;8;10].

Relevance of the Problem. The formation of an ileostomy is often a necessary and sometimes the only possible method for correcting intestinal pathology. According to summary statistics from several studies, among the conditions leading to ileostomy formation, colon cancer accounts for 43–76%, and benign tumors for 12–27%. Urgent intestinal conditions requiring ileostomy formation comprise 6–21% [3;4;7;8;10].

Experience shows that the known methods for forming ileotransversoanastomoses (ITA) have certain limitations, which justifies the further search for and improvement of these techniques [1;6].

Consequently, the development and implementation of new methods for intestinal anastomosis formation continue, with a primary focus on the prevention of anastomotic leakage [2;5;9]. Addressing these challenges allows for improved outcomes in the surgical treatment of this patient category.

Objective of the Study. The study aims to improve the outcomes of surgical treatment for intestinal diseases by optimizing surgical tactics.

Materials and Methods. The study included 93 patients with diseases of the large intestine (colon) who underwent right hemicolectomy with the formation of an end ileostomy, followed by reconstructive surgery (RS) in the form of ileotransversoanastomoses (ITA) at the Clinic of Andijan State Medical Institute.

According to the objectives of the study, the patients were conditionally divided into two groups:

- Comparison group: 2021–2022, including 54 patients (58.1%) with urgent intestinal diseases requiring ileostomy formation, where traditional surgical approaches were applied.
- Main group: 2023–2024, including 39 patients (41.9%) with urgent intestinal diseases requiring ileostomy formation, where optimized surgical tactics were implemented.

Patient distribution was carried out according to the WHO International Age Classification (2021).

To achieve the study objectives, general clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, and statistical research methods were applied in accordance with the protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and Discussion. According to the objectives of the study, the main group for 2024–2025 consisted of 39 patients (41.9%) with large intestine (colon) diseases who underwent right hemicolectomy with end ileostomy formation followed by ileotransversoanastomosis (ITA), where optimized surgical tactics were applied.

Patient distribution was carried out according to the WHO International Age Classification (2021).

Among the 39 patients, 26 (66.7%) were men and 13 (33.3%) were women. The largest proportion in the main group were patients aged 45–59 years – 23 (59.0%), representing the most economically active age group. A significant number of patients were aged 60 years and older – 11 (28.2%), and 19–44 years – 5 (12.8%). These data further emphasize the medical, economic, and social significance of the problem, as well as its high relevance.

In the main group, the majority of cases were colon tumors – 26 (66.7%) patients, which posed substantial challenges in determining surgical tactics and influenced disease prognosis. Of these, 20 (51.3%) were men and 6 (15.4%) were women.

Non-tumorous colon diseases accounted for 4 (10.3%) patients, of whom 3 (7.7%) were men and 1 (2.6%) was a woman. Colon injuries and trauma were indications for right hemicolectomy with ileostomy formation in 9 (23.1%) patients (6 men – 15.4% and 3 women – 7.7%).

The most frequent tumor localizations in the colon were:

- Cecum – 13 patients (44.8%)
- Hepatic flexure – 9 patients (31.0%)

Tumors in the lower third of the colon were found in 2 patients (6.9%), in the middle third – 2 patients (6.9%), and in the upper third – 3 patients (10.3%).

The prevalence of oncological disease was determined according to the international TNM classification system (7th edition, adopted in 2009, recommended for use from 2010).

Patients with colon tumors were diagnosed with stage II (T3-4N0M0) in 21 cases (72.4%) and stage III (T1-4N1-2M0) in 6 cases (20.7%). It should be noted that in the main group, stage I and IV tumors (T1-4N1-2M1) were not observed. At the same time, all patients had a complicated course of colon tumors.

Patients with colon tumors were predominantly admitted with a clinical picture of acute intestinal obstruction (AIO) in the subcompensation stage – 12 patients (41.4%) and in the decompensation stage – 13 patients (44.8%). In 4 patients (13.8%), AIO was accompanied by tumor perforation with development of purulent peritonitis.

Surgery for non-tumorous colon diseases was performed in 4 patients (10.3%) (3 men and 1 woman). The causes of non-tumorous diseases were:

- Complicated appendiceal infiltrate – 1 patient
- Dolichocolon – 1 patient
- Complicated diverticulosis – 2 patients

In 9 patients (23.1%), the indication for surgery was abdominal trauma, including 6 cases due to road traffic accidents and 3 cases of stab and cut wounds of the colon with purulent peritonitis, which required right hemicolectomy with end ileostomy formation.

The most frequent comorbid therapeutic conditions were:

- Cardiovascular diseases – 4 patients (10.3%) (ischemic heart disease, arrhythmias, post-infarction atherosclerosis)
 - Obesity – 5 patients (12.8%), which, along with metabolic disorders, often contributes to the development of malignancies
 - Anemia – 3 patients (7.7%), which, in our opinion, was associated with colon tumors
- Additionally, comorbid conditions included:

- Respiratory system diseases – 2 patients (5.1%) (bronchial asthma, pulmonary emphysema, chronic bronchitis)
- Hepatobiliary system disease – 1 patient (2.6%) (hepatitis C)
- Genitourinary system disease – 1 patient (2.6%) (chronic pyelonephritis)

The presence of severe comorbid therapeutic conditions created additional challenges in determining surgical tactics and in the surgical rehabilitation of the patients, given their initially severe condition.

Among combined surgical pathologies, the following were diagnosed: cholelithiasis – 1 case (2.6%), ventral hernias – 1 case (2.6%), ovarian cysts – 3 cases (7.6%), and uterine fibroids – 1 case (4.3%).

As noted, the study included only patients who had previously undergone right hemicolectomy with end ileostomy formation. Among them, 10 patients (25.6%) had their primary surgeries performed in other healthcare institutions in the Andijan region. Prior to admission for reconstructive restorative surgery (RRS) in the form of ileotransversoanastomosis (ITA) formation, patients were under continuous outpatient observation.

The stoma-carrying period before RRS ranged from 1.5 to 3 months, and 3–6 months in 8 (20.5%) and 1 (2.6%) patients, respectively (compared with the comparison group, the frequency of early RRS increased from 11.1% to 23.1%).

In the main comparison group, the stoma-carrying period before RRS was 7–12 months in only 3 patients (7.7%) (compared with the comparison group, the frequency of RRS within 7–12 months decreased from 68.5% to 7.7%), and 12 months or more in 27 patients (69.2%) (compared with the comparison group, the frequency of RRS at 12 months or more increased from 20.4% to 69.2%). This was due to specific treatment aimed at preventing tumor recurrence.

Among the studied patients, early complications developed in 7 cases (17.9%), including:

- Suppuration and infiltration of the stoma wound – 2 patients (5.1%)
- Peristomal dermatitis – 2 patients (5.1%)
- Skin hypergranulation – 3 patients (7.7%)

The high frequency of skin complications was associated with the enzymatic composition of the small intestine. It should be noted that in our patients, stoma complications such as bleeding, necrosis, evisceration, prolapse, or abscesses were not observed.

In 2 cases (5.1%), late stoma complications were diagnosed: ileostomy retraction in 1

case (2.5%) and scar-atrophic changes in 1 case (2.6%). The occurrence of late stoma complications had a significant negative impact on the surgical rehabilitation of the patients.

In the main group, we completely abandoned “side-to-side” and “end-to-side” ileotransversoanastomoses (ITA). Invagination ITA “end-to-side” was performed in 8 patients (20.5%). It should be noted that in recent years, we developed the “submerged” invagination ITA “end-to-side” technique, which was performed in 15 patients (38.5%).

With accumulated experience in this patient cohort, we developed a modified “submerged” invagination ITA “end-to-end” method. Using this technique, 16 patients (41.0%) were operated on.

Summary: Thus, during the course of this study, the use of invagination anastomoses, including the modified “submerged” ITA “end-to-end” method, along with an improved diagnostic and therapeutic algorithm, allowed us to optimize surgical tactics and improve outcomes in this patient cohort

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